
Family involvement, familiness and capacity for responsible engagement of family businesses: proposal for a conceptual framework

Implication familiale, familiness et capacité d'engagement responsable des entreprises familiales: proposition d'un cadre conceptuel

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Abstract

The topic of social responsibility of family businesses is currently receiving increasing attention. The literature provided to date generally mobilizes the concept of socio-emotional wealth (SEW), to distinguish family businesses from others. However, to refer to SEW as the only determinant of the behavior of the family business is very reductive. This concept does not take into account, on the one hand, the discretionary power enjoyed by family owners and managers, and on the other hand, the ability to achieve desired results. Indeed, the angle of view based on the SEW largely obscures a characteristic, which made a large consensus, namely the familiness. Despite the apparent importance of familiness as a resource that differentiates family businesses from non-family businesses, studies analyzing its effect on the responsible engagement of family businesses remain very rare. Our objective in this conceptual paper is to examine the links between familiness, as a set of resources and skills, due to family involvement, and responsible business behavior. Part of a new vein of family business research, which postulates that the pursuit of SEW represents only the aspect of behavior relating to will, and clearly ignores the aspect of ability.

Keywords: Family business, CSR, Familiness, Socio-emotional wealth, Resource theory and competence.

Résumé

Le thème de responsabilité sociétale des entreprises familiales reçoit actuellement une attention croissante. La littérature fournie à ce jour, mobilise généralement le concept de la richesse socio-émotionnelle (SEW), pour distinguer les entreprises familiales des autres. Toutefois, se référer à la SEW comme seul déterminant du comportement de l'entreprise familiale, est très réducteur. Ce concept ne tient pas compte, d'une part, le pouvoir discrétionnaire dont disposent les propriétaires et les gestionnaires familiaux, et d'autre part, les capacités à atteindre les résultats escomptés. En effet, l'angle de vue basé sur la SEW occulte largement une caractéristique, qui a fait largement consensus, à savoir le *familiness*. En dépit de l'importance apparente du *familiness* comme ressource qui différencie les entreprises familiales des entreprises non familiales, les études analysant son effet sur l'engagement responsable des entreprises familiales, restent très rares. Notre objectif dans ce papier, qui a une visée conceptuelle, est d'examiner les liens entre le *familiness*, comme un ensemble des ressources et compétences, dues à l'implication familiale, et le comportement responsable des entreprises. En s'inscrivant dans une nouvelle veine de recherche en entreprise familiale, qui postule que la poursuite de la SEW représente seulement l'aspect du comportement relatif à la volonté, et ignore clairement l'aspect de la capacité.

Mots Clé: Entreprise familiale, RSE, *Familiness*, Richesse socio-émotionnelle, Théorie des ressources et compétence.

Introduction

Family businesses are theoretically considered unique because of the influence of a particular group, the family (Pearson et al., 2014). In other words, the involvement of the family in the ownership, management, and governance of the firm provides the opportunity for particularistic behaviors that would either be impossible or more difficult in non-family firms (Chrisman et al., 2012). These particularistic behaviors may therefore be different in degree or/and nature, as they may affect different stakeholders. Moreover, existing work on responsible behavior in family firms confirms this particularism. However, the explanations, antecedents behind this particularism, provided are not numerous, shadowy areas persist.

Certainly, these questions have already taken part in the agendas of researchers, specifically those specializing in family businesses. In fact, a field of research on CSR in family businesses has emerged. Nevertheless, the work provided to date is not only limited, but, in our opinion, it is very reductionist. They focus mainly, through quantitative studies in particular, on the influence of the family's non-economic objectives on responsible behavior. They ignore an aspect that is widely recognized in the literature, namely family resources.

The distinctive behavior of family firms also derives from the unique resources created by the interactions between the family and business systems (Habbershon et al., 2003; Sirmon and Hitt, 2003; Habbershon and Williams, 1999). These unique family business resources, referred to by researchers as familiness, are considered complex, dynamic, and intangible (Habbershon and Williams, 1999). Depending on how they are managed, they can create both advantages and disadvantages in terms of family business performance (Sirmon and Hitt 2003)

Thus, it seems legitimate to ask the following question:

How could the influence of family involvement, through familiness, affect the responsible behavior of family businesses?

In this research, we propose to look at the particular character of responsible behavior in family businesses from another angle. In a logic of complementarity with what already exists, we will use an approach that is widely used to understand the responsible behavior of companies and family businesses separately, but not enough to understand responsible behavior in family businesses. This is the approach of resources, or their manifestation in family businesses, familiness.

Accordingly, our paper is structured as follows. Because of the broad and complex nature of familiness, after introducing RBV as a relevant approach to CSR for family businesses, we begin by identifying the unique family resources and capabilities that constitute it. We then discuss the links that may exist between familiness and responsible engagement. To do so, we refer to the relevant literature that focuses on RBV in the study of family businesses and in the study of business/society relations.

1. RBV: a new approach to CSR of family businesses

Although the majority of research provided to date indicates that family businesses are more socially responsible (Bingham et al., 2010) and environmentally successful (Berrone et al., 2010; Craig and Dibrell; 2006), or at least are more committed to avoiding socially irresponsible activities (Dyer and Whetten, 2006) and misbehavior (Ding and Wu, 2013), whether they are large firms (Berrone et al., 2010; Craig and Dibrell; 2006) or SMEs (Laguir and Elbaz, 2015, Berent et al., 2010; Berger-Douce, 2010; Uhlaner et al., 2012). Recently, a few studies have shown the lack of significant difference between family and non-family firms (Hirigoyen and Poulain-Rehm, 2014; Amann et al., 2012), or even the opportunism and irresponsibility of family firms (Fogel, 2006). Researchers in the family business field are increasingly calling for recognition of the heterogeneity of family organizations (Chrisman et al., 2005), and for more caution in generalizing results across all entities belonging to this organizational category, this includes the results of work on CSR and business ethics (Miller and Le Breton-Miller, 2016, Marques et al., 2014).

Researchers who argue for a superiority thesis (Cennamo et al., 2012, Berrone et al, 2010), or more nuancedly, a difference thesis (Cruz et al., 2014, Marques et al., 2014) of family businesses in relation to social, environmental and societal issues, generally resort to the recent construct of social-emotional wealth (SEW). Introduced in 2007 by Gómez-Mejía et al. this concept covers, according to Debicki al. (2016), "the range of non-financial benefits specifically related to the well-being and emotional needs of family members, arising from the operation of a business" (p.48). Indeed, these researchers argue that the pursuit of SEW - i.e., non-economic, family-centered goals - leads most family businesses to be more likely to engage with their stakeholders. In doing so, they draw on arguments from neo-institutional theory (Berrone et al, 2012), agency theory (Wiklund, 2006) and stewardship theory (Campopiano et al. 2014).

SEW clearly dominates the emerging field of research on CSR and business ethics in the context of family businesses, particularly Anglo-Saxon work. However, while very useful, this concept is insufficient. Certainly, as shown in several works (e.g., Naldi et al., 2013; Gomez-Mejia et al., 2011), the aspect of SEW pursuit plays a key role in conceptualizing the uniqueness of family firms compared to non-family firms. However, the mobilization of SEW dimensions as the primary determinant of family firm behavior fails to account for, on the one hand, the discretion that family owners and managers have in pursuing these non-economic concerns, and on the other hand, the capabilities to achieve the desired outcomes (i.e., resources) (See: Chrisman and Holt 2016). Indeed, this view largely obscures a characteristic, which has been a consensus in both the Francophone and Anglo-Saxon literature, during the first decade of this third millennium, namely familiness.

The concept of familiness, which captures the resources and skills held by the firm through family involvement (Habbershon and Williams, 1999), is a big hole in the literature on responsible family business behavior. Despite, on the one hand, the recurrence of the resource-based view (RBV) in many studies devoted to CSR (see Branco and Rodrigues, 2006), and on the other hand, the observation and recognition of the importance of social capital and social networks, on which familiness is based (Sharma, 2008), as a vector of appropriation of the CSR approach, especially in SMEs. In the sense that they constitute a source of motivation, learning, knowledge acquisition and development, support and accompaniment, and technological and information sharing for the CSR approach (Calme and Bonneveux, 2015; Bonneveux et al., 2011; Bonneveux and Saulquin, 2009, Berger-Douce, 2006, Auberger and Quairel, 2005). Furthermore, various authors suggest that familiness allows families to have a greater long-term orientation and an increase in continuity in their relationships with stakeholders (Carney, 2005; Morck and Yeung, 2003).

Despite this apparent importance of familiness as a resource that differentiates family firms from non-family firms, studies analyzing its effect on the responsible engagement of family firms, especially to understand the differences observed with respect to non-family firms, remain very scarce.

Indeed, the RBV, which assumes that the behavior of companies is largely attributable to resources and capabilities, is clearly a common denominator of the two fields questioned in this reflection: business and society and family business. On the one hand, it has been a privileged entry point to analyze the integration of sustainable development in the business strategy

(Ghera, 2010). It was mobilized to question the factors that are likely to promote the integration of environmental and social concerns, and in particular to explain the differences in the degree of commitment between large companies and SMEs. Variables such as size, innovation, financial status, and human resources are often used to explain the responsible behavior of SMEs (Robichaud et al., 2012; Berger-douce et al. 2008). On the other hand, the assertion that family businesses possess several unique resources (Cabrera-Suarez et al., 2001, Habbershon and Williams, 1999), appears in the majority of works referring to this organizational category. Several researchers (Arregle et al., 2007; Sharman & Manikuttu, 2005; Sirmon & Hitt, 2003) argue that family involvement can produce differences between family and non-family firms in terms of the level and nature of resources and the way in which these resources are deployed and exploited. These resources, which researchers refer to as the "familiness" of the firm, are repeatedly presented as the main sources of performance and competitiveness of family firms.

Our objective in the rest of this article, which has a conceptual focus, is to examine the link between familiness as a set of resources and skills due to family involvement and responsible behavior in family businesses. Following the new vein of research, which postulates that SEW might only affect the willingness and not the ability of the family business (For example: Chrisman and Holt, 2016; De Massis et al., 2014). We aim to explore theoretically how, and under what conditions, family resources might influence responsible family business behavior. While recognizing a heterogeneity of these organizations, due primarily to the degree of family involvement in each firm.

2. Family involvement and Familiness in family businesses.

It is generally accepted in the field of family business that family involvement in the business could be the origin of several complex, rare and inimitable resources and capabilities (Cabrera-Suarez et al., 2001; Chrisman et al., 2005; Habbershon and Williams, 1999; Sirmon And Hitt, 2003). This idea is not new, it is the culmination of a great scientific debate that began with the seminal work of Habbershon and Williams (1999).

At the end of the 1990s, the thesis of the superiority of family businesses over non-family businesses in terms of performance gained momentum. And it served to give legitimacy to the field, which had no solid theoretical foundation. At the time, despite empirical confirmation, there was not a sufficient explanation for this superiority. There were no conclusive models to understand the empirically observed high performance of family firms. In this regard,

Habbershon and Williams (1999) stated that "if we believe that family managers are a competitive advantage for family firms, then we need to determine: what kind of resource they are and under what conditions they add value" (p.10). Indeed, this self-criticism led to the emergence of the concept of familiness, a concept that is now crucial in the field of family business.

2.1 The familiness: nature and dimensions

Building their arguments and explanatory model on the theory of resources and competencies (RBV), Habbershon and Williams (1999) indicated that family firms are more successful because they have idiosyncratic resources. This unique set of family business resources, which stems from the family's involvement in the strategic and operational activities of the firm, is called "familiness." Thus, these two researchers introduced the term familiness into academic discussions of family businesses to refer to "*The unique bundle of resources a particular firm has because of the systems interaction between the family, its individual members, and the business*" (Habbershon & Williams, 1999, p. 11).

Familiness is a relatively new but critical concept for understanding family business. It has become one of the central concepts in family business research (Frank et al., 2010). The goal behind its introduction is to advance the understanding of the essence of family businesses. Familiarity is conceptualized from the RBV literature to explain the sources of strategic advantage in family firms, and it refers to the set of idiosyncratic resources and capabilities of a particular firm acquired as a result of the systemic interaction between the family and the firm. These family-centered resources lead to a firm's competitive advantage to the extent that they are valuable and inimitable by other firms. The value and inimitability of these idiosyncratic resources and capabilities is due to their socially complex, process-dependent, and often tacit nature (Habbershon & Williams, 1999).

After its introduction, the concept of familiness took on other dimensions. Its use has expanded beyond the RBV theory, which has led to much confusion about its appropriate use. While it was initially defined as the resources and capabilities that emerge when family and business coexist within the family firm. Subsequently, some researchers have used it to sometimes cover the influence of the family on the business more generally. For example, Zellweger et al (2010) developed a model to describe and explain familiness by distinguishing three dimensions: "the components of family involvement", which focus on family ownership, management and

control; "the essence of that involvement", which describes the effects of a family's behavior and abilities on the business; and "organizational identity", which is based on the identity of the family and the perception of the business, by the family, staff and customers, as a family business. Other researchers have mobilized it under the assumptions of other theories. Wiesmeier-Sammer et al (2013), in a literature review on familiness, revealed that, in addition to RBV, three main other theories that have been employed to discuss this concept: social capital theory, systems theory and agency theory. However, they confirm that familiness has mostly been incorporated within the RBV framework (Wiesmeier-Sammer et al, 2013).

To reduce this confusion over the use of the concept of familiness, authors have undertaken significant efforts to clarify the nature of the resources and dimensions of familiness (Irava and Moores, 2010; Pearson et al., 2008; Sharma, 2008). In these recent publications, researchers have attempted to identify that set of resources controlled by a firm, resulting from the continuous overlap of the family system with the firm system. In particular, they have highlighted the existence of resources such as social capital (Pearson et al., 2008; Sharma, 2008), physical capital (Miller and Le Breton-Miller, 2005; Steier, 2007), human capital (Puhakka, 2002), financial capital and survival capital (Sirmon and Hitt, 2003). More recently, based on data from four in-depth case studies, Irava and Moores (2010), have provided more detailed insights into the nature of familiness (Figure 1), arguing that the content of familiness consists of resources held at the individual level (reputation and experience), organizational resources (such as organizational learning), and transactional resources (such as the mobilization of family and professional networks).

Family involvement in the business through ownership, governance, management, and intentions for transgenerational succession and vision can also affect the development of psychological organizational capital (Memili et al., 2013). This intangible and valuable resource, according to Memili et al. (2013), consisting of hope, effectiveness, resilience, and optimism.

In addition, family businesses often have a particular corporate culture that can be influenced by the sustained presence of the family in the business, often referring to the attitudes and beliefs of the founders of these businesses (Poutziouris et al., 1997). These attitudes and beliefs have been considered as resources by some researchers.

The level of familiness varies from firm to firm and should not be considered a dichotomous concept for distinguishing between a family and non-family firm as used in the early work. Familiness is not an automatic result of having a family as a majority shareholder. Familiness

is cultivated and developed over time as the firm moves from one family generation to the next (Robic et al., 2015). Some family firms have high levels of familiness while other family firms have more similarities to non-family firms in terms of the level of familiness (Andersén, 2015). Thus, familiness may be a root of heterogeneity in family firms as it leads to individual idiosyncrasies.

Figure 1: the Familiness resource model

Source: Irava and Moores, 2010, p.138.

2.2 Familiness: an attribute with paradoxical effects

The notion of familiness in fact aims to capture the source of what is idiosyncratic about the resource profile of each family firm and provides a conceptual pathway for examining how family influence in the firm can lead to differences in performance. Habbershon and Williams' (1999) conceptualization work has served as a direction for other work, their concept of

familiness is used as an explanation of various relationships within family firms, or as a way to differentiate between family and non-family firms. Nevertheless, over time the concept has been refined. It has been theoretically developed and empirically tested in a variety of works. Thus, some researchers have questioned the thesis provided by Habbershon and Williams (1999). Family-influenced resources do not always improve firm performance. Instead, some attributes of familiness provide benefits in the resource management process, while others limit this ability (Sirmon & Hitt, 2003, p. 340). Habbershon et al. (2003) suggest that family involvement can drive or constrain performance depending on the nature of the resources, as well as the nature of the business activity. Similarly, Minichilli et al. (2010) argue that high levels of familiness may also be inversely related to firm performance. In other words, a specific resource inflicted by family can represent distinctive familiness ("f +"), when influences support the emergence of an advantage, as well as restrictive familiness ("f-"), when influences constrain and result in a disadvantage. While sometimes familiness is zero ("f0"), when family influences are neutral with respect to desired outcomes (Habbershon et al., 2003). The relationship between familiness as a resource and performance is not linear, but depends on what the family business in question does with it.

Table 1: Examples of paradoxes in the dimensions of familiness

Dimensions	Paradoxes (within the characteristic patterns)
Reputation	The founder's strong reputation presents a source of advantage for the firm and subsequent generations but it also places immense pressure and can hinder the ability of subsequent generations to establish their own reputation.
Experience—insights and skills	Outside the firm experiences are important for generating new skills and knowledge into the family business yet at the same time they can be in conflict with the values and the culture of the firm that has been passed down over generations of the family.
Decision-making	Quick decision-making have allowed agility and responsiveness to opportunities and threats. It has also led to expensive losses for the firms.
Learning	Informal learning has allowed the passage of the firm's culture and values across generations. It has also been a channel for the passage of not so desirable habits.
Relationships	Strain in relationships that both enhance and impede organisational processes.
Networks	Weak ties expand a firm's access to networks, information, and opportunities. However, they are more distant, financially driven, less loyalty (in comparison to weak ties)

Source: Irava and Moores, 2010, p. 139.

Moreover, in addition to research on the "what" dimension or the nature of resources, a second strand of the familiness literature addresses the "how", or how owners and managers of family firms are actually able or competent to aggregate and exploit their resource bases to create

competitive advantages (Sirmon & Hitt, 2003). In this regard, Sirmon and Hitt (2003) argue that family firms evaluate, acquire, juxtapose, aggregate, and exploit their resources differently than non-family firms. Naldi et al (2008) point out that family involvement in decision-making processes can be seen as a moderator that affects the ability to deploy intangible resources such as knowledge and reputation to their full potential to create financial performance. Kellermanns (2005) and Sharma and Manikutty (2005) point out that family firms may be biased by the personal preferences of family members with respect to adding and removing resources.

This work is based on extensions of resource theory that point out that owned or controlled resources do not directly produce positive outcomes for the firm. These resources also require management skills. Specifically, it is the use, deployment, and reconfiguration of resources that is the key to sustainable competitive advantage.

From this logic, the idea of resource management has emerged to focus on management actions that focus on structuring the resource portfolio, aggregating resources into capabilities and optimizing capabilities in family firms (Sirmon et al., 2007), and to emphasize the complex impact of familiness. As a result, researchers currently agree that familiness resources can only lead to competitive advantage and superior performance when they are managed to achieve their value-creating potential (Chirico et al., 2013; Sirmon et al., 2007).

Therefore, it is important to manage the paradoxical nature of the impact of familiness in order to simultaneously exploit its benefits and mitigate its drawbacks (Irava and Moores, 2010). A family business can suffer from constrictive familiness when it is not valued and managed or when the firm does not invest in replenishing, augmenting, and enhancing it as a valuable resource.

Familiness as a specific resource and/or skill is an important element of a family business's resource portfolio. The literature on this concept has focused largely on performance. However, work on the impact of familiness on strategic behavior is still somewhat limited. And those that do exist have focused mainly on entrepreneurial behavior.

Moreover, it is clear that the concept of familiness and the concept of SEW intersect in several areas. For example: social capital. However, it is important to note that these two concepts capture different realities. While SEW represents the aspiration of the family, familiness actually represents the stock of resources that are available to the family on a regular basis. The pursuit of building links with the different stakeholders, on the one hand, and the already

existing network of relationships ready for use, on the other, have different effects. So, which the first aspect influences the objectives and the will of the company. The second aspect influences the capacity of the company.

3. Familiness and capacity for responsible engagement

After approximately 20 years since its introduction into academic discussions of family businesses by Habbershon and Williams (1999), researchers agree that familiness is an important concept highlighting the uniqueness of family businesses (Chua et al., 2012; Sharma, 2004; Chrisman et al., 2003). However, as mentioned above, this concept has been used primarily, in the family business field, to understand and explain competitive advantage and financial performance (e.g.: Habbershon and Williams, 1999). However, Chrisman et al (2003) suggest that the degree of familiness within the family firm also leads to non-economic outcomes, such as the preservation of family ties or transgenerational value creation. However, this line of research has not been sufficiently explored. To our knowledge, no scientific work to date has mobilized the familiarity in the understanding of non-economic performance, in particular the social, environmental and societal performance of companies. This is due, in our opinion, to the noticeable dominance of the more recent concept of socio-emotional wealth in the field, especially during the last decade.

As already mentioned in the introduction, the RBV approach is widely used to understand and explain the responsible behavior of companies. Financial, human and information resources and skills such as stakeholder management capacity and innovation capacity are reported in several works as elements that are favorable to responsible corporate behavior.

Table 2: Typologies of resources and competences involved in an environmental strategy

Hart (1995)	Sharma et Vredenburg (1998)	Byusse et Verbeke (2003)	Bowen et Sharma (2005)
Employees' Habits	Stakeholder Integration	Environmental competence	Resource Margin
strategic planning process	Capacity for Continuous Innovation	Human competence	Combination of resources competences
Stakeholder management	Organizational learning capacity	Organizational competence	Dynamic capacity
Continuous innovation		Process competence	
New competence and technology		strategic planning competence	

Source : Gherra, 2010b, p:145.

In family businesses, in addition to the resources and capabilities related to the business, there are resources and capabilities related to family involvement and family-business interactions (Chrisman, Chua and Litz, 2003). To our knowledge, this surplus, which can include financial, human and social resources, is not sufficiently taken into account in the literature on responsible behavior. For this reason, we will attempt, in the remainder of this paper, to highlight some elements of theoretical reflection on the possible positive effects of the various components of familiness on the capacity of family businesses to engage in responsible behavior.

3.1 Patient financial capital

The financial resources of family businesses, especially small and medium-sized ones, are generally limited because of the desire to remain independent of banks or other equity holders. This fear of loss of control leads this type of organization to resort to self-financing as the main mode of financing, then to debt, and rarely to opening up the capital (Blondel, 2012). The other challenge limiting the use of external financing by family firms is the higher cost of capital: they generally have to pay higher interest rates than their peers (Morck et al., 2005). As a result, these firms do not have access to the traditional equity or debt markets that are available to many non-family firms and to large family firms that have already diluted intra-family ownership.

In contrast, family businesses generally provide effective structures for managing financial capital because they generally have a longer time horizon and are not as accountable for short-term results as many non-family, widely held businesses. In addition, the desire to perpetuate the business for future generations provides a particular incentive to manage capital effectively. This generational investment strategy creates patient capital.

Patient capital is financial capital that is invested without the threat of liquidation for long periods of time. It allows family leaders to think in generations rather than years. In essence, patient capital differs from typical financial capital because of the expected investment time. Family capitalism and long-term investment are naturally linked (Blondel, 2012). Many non-family businesses try to develop long-term and relational investors, but cannot do so because the financial markets are not characterized by this investment strategy, they are indeed subject to the demands of the short term. However, thanks to patient capital, family businesses often take a long-term perspective. As a result, this extended time frame allows them to develop a mindset that makes them better able to pursue future business opportunities and allows them to

be more "exploratory" (Kellermanns & Eddleston, 2006). Thus, firms with patient capital are able to pursue more creative and innovative strategies. Otherwise, patient capital is a valuable asset for family businesses in that it allows for far-sighted investments that serve the ends of the organization rather than the ends of shareholders.

Patient capital can be particularly useful for responsible engagement. It provides family business managers with more opportunity to pursue responsible activities that generally take longer to pay off. Indeed, several researchers have emphasized the need for a long-term view in addressing CSR issues (e.g., Hart, 1995). In fact, the essence of the Brundtland Report's definition of sustainable development as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" emphasizes the importance of a long-term orientation.

Proposition 1: The high level of patient capital in family businesses increases their capacity for responsible engagement.

3.2 Family social capital

The concept of social capital reflects a complex set of dynamic relationships that exist within a group. Specifically, it refers to "the sum of the actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or a social unit" (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998, p 243, cited in Carr et al., 2011, p: 1208). The resources that can be provided by networks are diverse and varied. They have been specified, by Hitt et al. (2001), as complementary information, technologies, markets and financial resources.

According to much work in the field of family business, family firms are more predisposed to excel in creating and maintaining stable and sustainable relationships not only internally, but also with external stakeholders (Schulze & Gedajlovic, 2010). Their long-term perspective gives them the opportunity to develop long-term relationships with employees, banks, suppliers and important customers (Le Breton-Miller & Miller, 2006).

Time is important for the development of social capital, because social capital depends to a large extent on the stability and continuity of the social structure. In family businesses, networks develop over generations on the basis of family values and norms. This family-based social capital best distinguishes family businesses from non-family businesses. Non-family businesses can hire human resources, just as they can obtain financial resources. However, family social

capital cannot be rented or imported; it exists in family relationships (Sorenson, 2009). Indeed, individuals employed in non-family businesses often bring few, if any, of their pre-existing ties and networks to the workplace. In contrast, families have an abundance of stronger, more intense networks that can be appropriated by their businesses. In this perspective, Arregle et al (2007, p.77) confirm that family social capital is "*One of the most enduring and powerful forms of social capital*".

Family social capital is repeatedly recognized by family business scholars as an important mechanism by which family owners protect and nurture their family businesses (e.g., Arregle et al., 2004, Habbershon and Williams, 1999). However, when the network focuses solely on kinship and friendship, it may be too homogeneous to provide a diverse range of resources (Anderson, Jack, & Dodd, 2005). In this context, it is likely that as the family grows, the group becomes more heterogeneous - the frequency of contact and diversity of ties becomes more important (Kellermanns & Eddleston, 2007).

Considering this complexity, Pearson et al (2008) suggest a model that distinguishes the specific elements of family social capital. They suggest that social capital is manifested through the structural dimension of the family, the cognitive dimension of the family and the relational dimension of the family. While the structural dimension refers to the set of ties between individuals and contains the density, connectivity of ties, and the ability of members to use and reuse these social networks. The cognitive dimension of social capital refers to the shared representations, interpretations and systems of meaning among individuals and includes the group's shared vision and goals, as well as the unique language, stories and culture of a collective, commonly known, understood and deeply embedded. These structural and cognitive dimensions are antecedents to the relational dimension, referring to the resources created and leveraged by relationships (Pearson et al., 2008), including trust, norms, obligations, expectations, and identification (Dawson, 2012).

These relationships that develop between family members and stakeholders (e.g., friends, customers, business partners, community leaders, etc.) stem from their embeddedness in their communities and can bring unique benefits to family businesses. In particular, access and effective information exchange (Coleman, 1988). They foster trust and can therefore provide access to important external financial resources. In addition, connections with different stakeholders can provide industry-specific knowledge and help family businesses recognize the need to adapt to environmental change more quickly (Pearson et al., 2008). In addition, the

focus on long-term relationships, resulting in connectivity to customers and suppliers, provides a superior position for opportunity identification, recognition, and exploration (Cao et al., 2009). As it makes it easier to communicate the value of the firm's goods and services to potential customers (Lounsbury and Glynn, 2001).

Family social capital also influences behaviors, such as collective actions, cooperation and commitment to common goals. In its structural dimension, it is recognized as a determinant of the family firm's commitment to goals related to non-family stakeholders such as customers, employees and society (Cabrera-Suarez et al. 2014). Strong ties decrease the likelihood of opportunism (Coleman, 1988), and encourage family members to act as stewards and create conditions for ethical behavior within the firm (Le Breton-Miller & Miller, 2009). In the same vein, Long and Mathews (2011) confirm that frequent interactions, high interdependence, and network closure, can lead to ethical behavior by family leaders toward network members.

Thus, family social capital is a valuable resource because it reduces transaction costs, solves internal coordination problems, and provides access to important resources through external networks such as: information, knowledge, technology, etc. It is a "social infrastructure" that makes it easier to engage with stakeholders. It is a "social infrastructure" that makes it easier to engage with stakeholders. It contributes to the ability of a company to create value in the form of innovation by facilitating the combination and exchange of resources within a company. From this perspective we suggest that family social capital has several potential sources of the family firm's ability to engage on social, environmental and societal issues.

Proposition 2: A high level of family social capital in family businesses increases their capacity for responsible engagement.

3.3 Family human capital.

For Sirmon and Hit (2003), human capital represents the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of an individual that enable unique and new actions. On this resource, family businesses are also specific. Researchers recognize that the human capital of family members is more unique and complex than non-family members due to their simultaneous involvement in the family and the business (Dawson, 2012; Sirmon & Hitt, 2003).

Family descendants often become involved in the family business at a young age, which gives them the opportunity to develop deep, usually tacit, business-specific knowledge (Dyer, 2006;

Sirmon and Hitt, 2003). Knowledge that is particularly related to "how to do business." Through informal conversations at the dinner table, watching their parents at work, or through summer employment in their parents' businesses, children understand how to make products, find customers, and make sales. In addition, parents or other family members communicate both the mechanics and the art associated with running a business. This allows children, the future leaders of the business to gain specific, and difficult to codify, tacit knowledge about the business that is typically inaccessible to non-family members (Dyer et al., 2014).

Thus, family involvement provides an intangible resource to family businesses. They create what researchers call family human capital. Considered as a combination of knowledge, experience, and individual abilities of family members, which they have gained and developed through personal beliefs, values, education, and direct exposure to business issues, and which are transferred from one generation to another throughout the family's existence in the business (Dawson, 2012).

The stock of this family human capital, which comes from the heads of individuals, varies from one family business to another. Like other family resources, it is most important when the family is heavily involved in the firm, when this involvement lasts over time, and when spouses are included in the firm (Sorenson et al., 2009). Even family members who are not employed in the firm are likely to make human capital available to the firm when it gives them advice (Blondel, 2012), and when they have positive social relationships (Sorenson et al., 2009). For, as Coleman (1988) indicates, social capital influences the creation of human capital for subsequent generations.

Compared to non-family businesses, family businesses can enjoy several advantages, thanks to family human capital. In other words, the knowledge and skills of family members are considered by researchers as a factor of longevity and performance in family businesses (Dawson, 2012). Cabrera-Suarez et al. (2001) emphasize the importance of knowledge and expertise as a source of competitive advantage in family businesses. Bjuggren et al. (2001) point out that there is a form of family idiosyncratic knowledge that makes intergenerational succession in the family more profitable than other types of succession. In this regard, Cabrera-Suarez et al, (2001, p.39) argue that "family firm's specific knowledge, as well as the ability to create and transfer it, are considered a key strategic asset that may be positively associated with higher level of performance".

In addition to its effect on performance, family human capital incentivizes the pursuit of wealth creation, sustains entrepreneurial activities, and fosters the recognition of opportunities (Dawson, 2012). In addition, Ward (2009), when enumerating the ten "hidden arts" that are key to the success of long-term family businesses, indicates that the first art is the skill of resolving paradoxes. Schuman et al (2010) confirm that family businesses have a head start in dealing with paradox and add that a formidable ability to recognize the presence of paradoxes is built into their DNA.

In this sense, family human capital seems to provide capabilities that have been repeatedly recognized as determinants of responsible behavior. For example, Berger-Douce and Gherib (2012) indicate that the entrepreneurial profile of the leader positively influences his or her environmental commitment. Furthermore, Hahn et al. (2015) and Scherer et al. (2013) argue that the ability to manage paradoxes increases the social performance of family firms. Accordingly, we argue that high family human capital is likely to increase the ability of family firms to behave responsibly.

Proposition 3: High family human capital in family businesses increases their capacity for responsible engagement.

4. Conclusion

Familiness is one of the strategic factors that make family businesses unique and allow them to develop family-based competitive advantages (Habbershon and Williams 1999; Habbershon et al. 2003). It is not available for all family businesses, or at least not of equal weight. The degree of family involvement in the firm and the duration of that involvement are recognized, so far, as the main origins of the heterogeneity of family firms in this respect. The greater the degree of family involvement, the greater the potential of family resources. And the older the age of the family business, the greater the potential of family skills. Nevertheless, these distinctive conditions and antecedents of familiness have not yet been fully identified (Irava and Moores, 2010).

This rather distinctive resource can positively influence the company's propensity to undertake responsible activity by enhancing its capabilities. However, we suggest, despite the above developments, that its existence is not a guarantee of responsibility. While a family business may have high family resources conducive to responsible behavior, it will not achieve responsible engagement unless the business has, in addition to the capabilities to effectively use and manage family resources, the will to pursue responsible behavior.

References

- [1] Amann, B, Jaussaudb, J. y Martineza, I. (2012). Corporate social responsibility in Japan: Family and nonfamily business differences and determinants. *Asian Business & Management*, 11 (3): 329–345.
- [2] Andersén J. (2015). The absorptive capacity of family firms – how familiness affects potential and realized absorptive capacity. *Journal of Family Business Management*, 5(1):73-89.
- [3] Antheaume N., Robic P. et Barbelivien D. (2013). French family business and longevity: Have they been conducting sustainable development policies before it became a fashion?. *Business History* 55 (6): 942–962.
- [4] Berger-Douce S. (2010). L’engagement environnemental des PME familiales. *Gestion* 2000, 5(10): 49-63.
- [5] Berrone, P., Cruz, C., & Gómez-Mejía, L.R. (2012). Socioemotional wealth in family firms: Theoretical dimensions, assessment approaches, and agenda for future research. *Family Business Review*, 25(3), 258–279.
- [6] Berrone, P., Cruz, C., Gomez-Mejia, L., & Larraza-Kintana, M. (2010). Socioemotional wealth and corporate responses to institutional pressures: Do family-controlled firms pollute less?, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 55, 82-113.
- [7] Berent-Braun, M.M. and Uhlaner, L.M, (2012). Responsible ownership behaviors and financial performance in family owned businesses, *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 19 (1): 20 – 38.
- [8] Berger-Douce S., Gherib J. (2012). Entrepreneurial Profile and Environmental Commitment of SMEs: A Comparative Analysis in France and in Tunisia. *International Business Research*. 5, (7) 2012.
- [9] Blondel C. (2012). Investissement à long terme et capitalisme familial. *Revue d'économie financière* 2012/4 (108) : 57-68.
- [10] Campopiano, G., De Massis, A., & Chirico, F. (2014). Firm philanthropy in small and medium-sized family firms: The effects of family involvement in ownership and management. *Family Business Review*, 27: 244-258.
- [11] Cennamo, C., Berrone, P., Cruz, C., & Gomez-Mejia, L. R. (2012). Socioemotional wealth and proactive stakeholder engagement: Why family-controlled firms care more about their stakeholders. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 36: 1153-1173.

- [12] Coville T, (2014). L'entreprise familiale est-elle éthique ?, *Revue de l'Entrepreneuriat* 3 (13):73-97.
- [13] Chrisman, J.J., Chua, J.H., De Massis, A., Minola, T., & Vismara, S. (2016). Management processes and strategy execution in family firms: from “what” to “how”. *Small Business Economics*, 47: 719–7347.
- [14] Chrisman, J. J., Chua, J. H., & Steier, L. (2005). Sources and consequences of distinct familiness: An introduction. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 29(3), 237–247.
- [15] Cruz, C. et Larraza-Kintana M., Garcés-Galdeano L., Berrone P. (2014). are family firms really more socially responsible?, *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, [38 \(6\)](#): 1295–1316.
- [16] Coleman, J. S. (1988). Social capital in the creation of human capital. *American Journal of Sociology*. (94) 95- 120.
- [17] Dawson, A. (2012). Human capital in family businesses: Focusing on the individual level. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 3: 3–11.
- [18] Dyer WG (2006). Examining the “family effect” on firm performance. *Family Business Review*, 19(4): 253-273.
- [19] Dyer, W. G., E. Nenque, and E. J. Hill (2014). Toward a Theory of Family Capital and Entrepreneurship: Antecedents and Outcomes. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 52(2), 266- 285.
- [20] Danes, S. M., Stafford, K., Haynes, G., & Amarapurkar, S. S. (2009). Family capital of family firms: Bridging human, social, and financial capital. *Family Business Review*, 22, 199–216.
- [21] Elbaz J., Laguir I. (2014). Family Businesses And Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Orientation: A Study Of Moroccan Family Firms, *The Journal of Applied Business Research*, 303: 671-688.
- [22] Fogel, K. (2006). Oligarchic family control, social economic outcomes, and the quality of government. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 37(5): 603–622.
- [23] Frank, H., Lueger, M., Nosé, L., and Suchy, D. (2010), ‘The concept of “familiness”’: literature review and systems theory based reflections’. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 1, (3), 119–130.
- [24] Gallo, M. A. (2004). The family business and its social responsibilities, *Family Business Review*, 17: 135-149.

- [25] Gherra S.(2010a). « Stratégies de développement durable » Combiner les parties prenantes et les ressources et compétences de l'entreprise. *Revue française de gestion*, 2010/5 n° 204, 141-153.
- [26] Gherra S. (2010b). *Intégration du développement durable dans la stratégie d'entreprise: une explication par la théorie des ressources et compétences et l'approche des parties prenantes. Le cas du secteur des produits de grande consommation. Thèse de doctorat en sciences de gestion, Aix-Marseille 2.*
- [27] Gómez-Mejía, L.R., Cruz, C., Berrone, P., & De Castro, J. (2011). The bind that ties: Socioemotional wealth preservation in family firms. *The Academy of Management Annals*, 5(1), 653–707.
- [28] Gómez-Mejía, L.R., Takacs-Haynes, K., Nunez-Nicker, M., Jacobson, K.J.L., & Moyano-Fuentes, J. (2007). Socioemotional wealth and business risks in family-controlled firms: Evidence from Spanish olive mills. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 52(1), 106–137.
- [29] Habbershon, T.G. & Williams, M. (1999). A resource-based framework for assessing the strategic advantages of family firms. *Family Business Review*, 12(1), 1–25.
- [30] Hirigoyen G., Poulain-Rehm T. (2014). The Corporate Social Responsibility of Family Businesses: An International Approach, *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 2: 240–265.
- [31] Hoffman, J., Hoelscher, M., & Sorenson, R. (2006). Achieving sustained competitive advantage: A family capital theory. *Family Business Review*, 19, 135-145.
- [32] Irava, W.J., and Moores, K. (2010). Clarifying the strategic advantage of familiness: unbundling its dimensions and highlighting its paradoxes. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 1 (3): 131–144.
- [33] Marques, P., Preses, P., & Simon, A. (2014). The heterogeneity of family firms in CSR engagement: The role of values, *Family Business Review*, 27: 206-227.
- [34] Memili, E., Welsh, D.H.B., & Luthans, F. (2013). Going beyond research on goal setting: A proposed role for organizational psychological capital of family firms. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 37(6): 1289–1296.
- [35] Memili, E., Welsh, D.B., Kaciak, E., 2014. Organizational Psychological Capital of Family Franchise Firms Through the Lens of the Leader–Member Exchange Theory. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*. 21 (2): 200–209.

- [36] Nadi M. (2016). Contribution à l'analyse de l'influence de l'implication familiale sur le comportement responsable de l'entreprise: cas de quatre entreprises familiales marocaines. Thèse de doctorat en sciences de gestion. Université Cadi Ayyad Marrakech.
- [37] Robic P., Barbelivien D., Antheaume N., (2015) « Comment cultiver une ressource ? Outils de gestion et culture du familiness », *Management & Avenir* 2015/5 (79): 105-124.
- [38] Robichaud Y., Stocky C., Legrand N., godard C. (2012), « Les facteurs explicatifs de l'engagement environnemental des PME dans le secteur de l'agroalimentaire : une étude comparative Canada-France-Finlande », AIMS.
- [39] Rau, S. B. (2014). 'Resource-based view of family firms', in Melin, L., Nordqvist, M. and Sharma, P. (eds), *The SAGE Handbook of Family Business*, London: SAGE, pp. 321– 39.
- [40] Sorenson, R., & Bierman, L. (2009). Family capital, family business, and free enterprise. *Family Business Review*, 22, 193-195.
- [41] Uhlaner, L. M., van Goor-Balk, H. A., & Masurel, E. (2004). Family business and corporate social responsibility in a sample of Dutch firms, *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 11: 186-194.
- [42] Van Gils A., Dibrell C., Neubaum D. O., Craig J. B. (2014). Social Issues in the Family Enterprise, *Family Business Review*, 27 (3): 193-205.
- [43] Weismeier-Sammer, D., Frank, H., & von Schlippe, A. (2013). Untangling “familiness”: A literature review and directions for future research. *International Journal for Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 14(3), 165–177.
- [44] Zellweger, T., Eddleston, K., & Kellermans, F. (2010). Exploring the concept of familiness: Introducing family firm identity. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 1, 54–63.